

Building Research Software Communities: How to increase engagement in your community

 Daniel Nüst³

1 Imperial College London, UK **2** ReSA, University of Melbourne, Australia **3** University of Münster, Germany

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4430811](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4430811)

Software

- [SORSE](#)
- [Event Website](#)

Category: workshops

Published: December 11, 2020

License

Authors of papers retain copyright and release the work under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License ([CC-BY](#)).

Communities are a very important aspect of the development and sustainability of research software engineering. It was as [the result of a community meeting](#) back in 2012 that the Research Software Engineering (RSE) movement came about. This goes to show the potential power of a group of individuals coming together from a range of different research backgrounds with common challenges, important ideas and a desire to drive change. Research software communities provide a place for RSEs and researchers to build knowledge, develop networks and find collaborators. They also provide a space to develop policies and advocate for the importance of RSE and the best practices it promotes.

This workshop will investigate the challenges of building, developing and sustaining research software communities. The workshop scope includes communities at all levels - international, national, regional and local - and a range of topics, both general and discipline-specific. The workshop will be interactive and will provide opportunities for participants to apply knowledge gained to challenges they may have in trying to set up or grow their own communities, and to engage in group discussion to support this.

There is already significant expertise in community development and engagement in a variety of areas of the research community. This workshop will aim to bring together a range of different perspectives and ideas from representatives from different types of communities along with resources on community development and engagement from relevant groups. It will consist of two 2-hour sessions over two days.

The workshop will draw upon experiences from a range of research software communities, including national RSE chapters, e.g., [de-RSE chapters](#). The workshop will build on the [Community of Open Scholarship Grassroots Networks](#) (COSGN) concept that the [Research Software Alliance](#) (ReSA) created to support the community development element of grassroots initiatives in open source software.